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Impact Factor: 0.98

IMPACT OF RETAILING BRANDED ITEMS THROUGH SHOPPING MALLS ON CUSTOMERS' PURCHASE BEHAVIOR

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ABSTRACT

The Indian textile and apparel industry holds a unique role in the economy. It contributes about 7 percent to the GDP of the country. The Textile and Clothing Industry, the second largest employer after agriculture, provides jobs for more than 37 million people. The fundamental objective of this research paper is to enhance our knowledge of the malls and the various leading companies in this sector, as these companies will respond in quota-free periods in the Indian retail market and to what extent these companies will generate wealth from the various promotional schemes for their stakeholders. Each segment takes us step by step from the previous results, the current scenario, and the mall's potential reactions. The thesis rests on the basis of research work conducted and its conclusion. Several studies have been carried out to interpret the outcome. The analysis shows preferential requirements for consumer apparel purchases. It also offers insights into the preference for structured and unorganised shops and explanations that could be beneficial for marketers to reinvent strategies.

Key words: Branded Items, Purchasing Behavior, Retail Shopping Mall, Impetuous Buying.

INTRODUCTION

India's mall culture has evolved at an unprecedented rate. People had to make a choice between shopping, movies or hanging out on a holiday just a few years ago, but thanks to our malls, all these jobs can be done at the same time, under the same roof and with a great experience too. And when it comes to malls, it is literally the experience and not the purpose that counts. People find these malls to be the perfect place to shop or hang out in the summer heat as they provide free access to a fully air-conditioned complex with good music playing around and plenty of space for window shopping that is enjoyed by one and all. Not to mention the multiple food joints that serve various cuisines intended to magnetise all the foodies' taste buds. While malls are equally common among all ages, the real lovers of multiplexes are the young people for whom malls are the 'ultimate place to be. Malls serve their various purposes, such as shopping, watching movies, dating or just hanging out, although they don't really need a reason to be there.

Experts say malls are becoming larger across the nation as they are now positioned as a one-stop-shop for shopping, entertainment, recreation and eating-out needs rather than a destination for fashion items just to shop. The North Zone would account for 39 % of the total mall room by 2007, accompanied by the West Zone (33%), the South Zone (18%) and the East Zone (10%), according to the Images report. The study said much more action was anticipated from the smaller cities in the years ahead on the mall growth front. These

cities will have about 12.8 million sq ft of mall space by 2007, with about 2.5 million sq ft for Ludhiana and about 3.4 million sq ft for Ahmadabad. The global clothing, accessories & luxury market is likely to rise by 4.5 percent annually, according to a study by Data Monitor (2010), and the Asia Pacific region is expected to achieve a leadership role by 2015. There are a lot of obstacles for a marketer in the apparel industry in India. India's share in the world trade in apparel has so far been marginal (less than 3%). The world's apparel trade is valued at about US\$ 195 trillion annually. China produces over \$50 billion, followed by Mexico producing over \$8 billion, followed by many countries such as India, Sri Lanka and Bangladesh, the third largest producer and distributor of clothing worth \$5-6 billion annually.

The textile & apparel sector is one of the most dynamic and well-established industries in Gujarat, providing ample opportunities for jobs. The "Manchester of the East" and the "Denim City" were referred to as Ahmadabad City of Gujarat. Surat is the strongest base for synthetic fabrics in India and is generally referred to as the "Silky City sparkling with diamonds". In Gujarat, the textile industry contributes 6 percent to the total industrial production of cotton producer (35 percent) and exporter (60 percent). Export goods include raw cotton, synthetic products, denim, processed & textured yarn, grey woven & knitted fabrics, non-woven fabrics, bed linen and garments, accounting for 12 percent of India's textile exports in the organised market. Europe, the Middle East, China, Thailand, Turkey, the USA, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh and Brazil are export destinations

LITERATURE REVIEW:

A confirmatory review and refinement of the PRECON scale studied Prestige apparel shopping by customers by Deeter-Schmelz, Dawn R.; Moore, Jesse N.; Goebel, Daniel J, (2000). Aspects studied include context on the symbolic aspects of consumption; prestige shopping behaviour; PRECON scale reassessment and refinement; and the effect on prestige shopping of income and age. The paper ends with managerial consequences for prestige apparel retailers in the U.S.

Kincade, Doris H.; Woodard, Ginger A.; Park, Haesun (2002) researched buyer-seller relationships in the apparel industry that are crucial for success in promotional support. The aim of the study was to define the categories of promotional support offered by manufacturers to apparel retailers, to identify the retailer's perceptions of the frequency of offering and the importance of promotional support, and to investigate the relationship between frequency of offering and perceptions of importance. The findings showed that monetary support was considered to be the most significant promotional support. A strong and significant correlation was found between products viewed as important by consumers and the frequency of these items' offerings.

The Long-term Impact of Loyalty Programs on Consumer Purchase Behavior and Loyalty was discovered by Liu, Yuping (2007). The study found that consumers who were heavy buyers at the beginning of a loyalty programme were most likely to claim their qualified rewards using longitudinal data from a convenience store franchise, but the programme did not prompt them to change their purchasing behaviour. Consumers whose initial levels of patronage were low or moderate, on the other hand, steadily bought more and became more loyal to the company. The loyalty programme extended their relationship with the company into other market areas for light customers. In order to assess incentives for loyalty schemes, there is also a need to recognise patronage.

Hyllegard, Karen; Eckman, Molly; Descals, Alejandro Molla; Borja, Miguel Angel Gomez (2005), researched the impressions of Spanish customers of goods and services of US apparel

specialty retailers. The study stressed that the success of specialty retailers in international markets depends on their awareness of culturally identified values, norms and behaviour that affect the decision-making of consumers and the acceptance of products and services. The study analysed the conduct of customer store patronage and apparel buying, recognition of US apparel brands, perceptions of goods and services from retailers, and perceptions of the effect on local communities of international retailers. It found that the expectations varied in terms of quality, fashionability, product assortment, customer service reach and quality, location comfort, payment options, national brands and store layout. The acceptance of US apparel brands by consumers was a function of age, household income, country of production and price of apparel items. Merging developments in new retail formats & Indian Scenario Consumer Shopping Behavior:

A Meta Analysis & Review; Aditya P. Tripathi The Indian retail sector is undergoing a transformation and its growth and investment pattern is undergoing a major shift in this emerging market. There are new retail formats being experimented with by both current and new players. Two famous formats are currently rising at a rapid pace in hypermarkets and supermarkets. The brick-click and click-click formats are also increasingly functional in the Indian retail environment, apart from the brick-mortar formats. Market dynamics are also evolving in India, and retailers need to take this into account and formulate their strategies and tactics to provide the customer with the exact predicted value.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

A research design is a structure or model for a marketing research project to be carried out. It details the procedures used to acquire the information needed to structure and/or solve the problems of marketing research. Conclusive analysis allows the decision-maker to define, assess and choose the best course of action to be taken in a given situation. Some of the goals are to research the changes in customer purchasing behaviour due to the creation of a shopping mall with a specific emphasis on branded apparel, to study the factors influencing the purchase of branded apparel, to identify the reasons behind the organised and unorganised outlet's purchase of branded apparel, to identify the effect when the promotional scheme is implemented Sampling plan includes Sample area; in this case New city, Sample size: in this case 200 respondents adopting convenient sampling.

DATA ANALYSIS:

There are 139 participants in the research who are male, while 61 participants are female. 53.5 percent of respondents are between 20 and 30 years of age, and 41.5 percent are between 30 and 40 years of age. The majority of respondents are highly qualified. 60 % of respondents are postgraduates, while 29.5% are graduates. 20.5 percent, 21 percent, 18.5 percent, 20.5 percent, 10000-20000, 20000-30000, 30000-40000, and 40000-50000, respectively, monthly family income.

Research shows that 46% of our respondents buy from the mall, while 11 % of respondents buy from the unorganised outlet, while 43 % of respondents buy from both outlets, indicating that the future of both outlets will be bright.

Researcher finds that 43 % of respondents, i.e. 83% of 200 respondents like to buy at the time of the festival while 23.5% of respondents like to buy at the time of the financial scheme while 26.5% of respondents like to buy at the time of the promotional scheme while the remaining respondent says that there is no fixed transaction that includes others. At the time of buying branded clothing, 38.5% of our respondents spend on average between Rs 500-1000 per month while 31 % of respondents spend more than Rs 1500 while 21 % of respondents spend between Rs1000-1500 while the rest of

respondents spend between Rs100-500. 136 out of 200 respondents, the frequency of purchasing branded apparel is 1 to 2 times per month, while 59 respondents visit frequency is 3 to 4 times, while 5 respondents out of 200 sample size are more than 4 times purchaser. Highest respondent, i.e. 42 percent of respondents at 6 p.m. to 10 p.m. are like purchasing branded clothing, while the time between 1 p.m. and 3 p.m. is when respondents least choose to buy branded apparels. 45.5 percent of respondents buy branded clothing from the mall due to good quality, while 40 percent buy value for money while customer service is least influenced by the reason for purchasing branded clothing from the mall. At the time of the promotional scheme, the majority of respondents, i.e. 89% of respondents are affected by the purchase of branded apparel while the rest of the respondents are not affected by the promotional scheme.

From the weighted average, we find that at the time of purchase from the organised market, consumers offer access to all products as their first priority. The financial system is the second priority when the consumer buys from the organised market, the third priority when the consumer buys from the organised market, and the fourth priority when the consumer buys from the organised market. Promotional framework as a fifth priority, contact with sales people as a sixth priority when purchasing consumers from the organised market.

At the time of their purchase from the unorganized market, respondents offer trusted brands (by providers) as their first priority. Proximity / convenience as their second priority, owner trust as their third priority, promotion as a priority, and financial services availability as their fifth priority at the time of purchase from the unorganised market.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Ho1: There is no important association between sales and purchase frequency.

Therefore, null hypothesis is dismissed where the sense value of the test is .027 is less than .05. There is, therefore, an essential relationship between sales and purchase frequency. It can also be said that there is a major relationship between the purchasing of revenue and frequency.

Ho2: expenditures made by the respondent are independent of the respondent 's revenue.

Since the magnitude of significance is less than .005, the null hypothesis is dismissed. It means the respondent's expenses are contingent on their family's income.

Ho3: Respondent expenditures are independent of the frequency of buying clothes from the mall.

Since the magnitude of significance is less than .05, the null hypothesis is dismissed. It implies that the respondent 's cost depends on the frequency of the transaction he made.

Ho4: There is no important correlation between education and purchases from an organised sector.

Because the value of meaning is greater than .05, it means the null hypothesis can not be dismissed. This implies that there is no relationship of importance between education and purchasing from an organised or unorganised market.

Ho5: There is no association of significance between income and various clothing buying circumstances.

Since the magnitude of significance is less than .05, the null hypothesis is dismissed. It also implies that there is an significant relationship between sales and transactions from various situations.

SUGGESTIONS/CONCLUSION

Since there is a rivalry between Organized & Unorganized for the bottle neck, measurement measures must be taken to resolve the field of weakness in Unorganized with respect to Organized. As their first choice, the consumer considers consistency and variety, so the outlet can place more focus on this. As most customers want to buy between 6 p.m. Towards 10 p.m. They should try to move demand from peak to low time so that consumers can serve well and their level of satisfaction can be improved by 37.5 percent and 25.5 percent of respondents agree and strongly agree that apparel prices in malls are high relative to local outlets, so coordinated outlets should try to keep their apparel prices lower in the long run on the market. As consumers spend tonnes on branded apparel, they can inspire them to spend more on apparel by adding more clothing range, promotional scheme, and quality clothing.

Organized consumer Apparel outlet means big investment, accessibility at one place of all brands, their presence in major Indian cities, professionalism, etc. Unorganized consumer Apparel outlet is characterised by the unavailability of all brands or the only available unique brands by the respondents, special schemes are there, financial schemes are typically preferred route. When buying branded Clothing, the promotional schemes to buy it are usually favoured by most of the respondents. Both structured and unorganised stores are commonly favoured by customers. The organised stores such as Big Bazaar are the most favoured in New Delhi to buy their consumer Apparel. Consumers enjoy the choice of all labels, clothing quality , variety & show when buying from a coordinated outlet. Consumers prefer the trustworthiness of owners and usability of financial services when buying from an unorganised source. Customers tend to wait for the discount available to buy branded clothing. Respondents believe that attractive fabric displays inspire them to buy branded clothing. Respondents also accept that advertised clothing rates are high relative to small shops in the mall. The consumer preferred to buy branded clothes rather than credit card by means of cash.

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